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Nonadjacent Demagnetisation Detection in Direct-Drive Permanent Magnet Generators for Renewable Energy Systems

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ABSTRACT

Advancement of renewable energy technologies placed tidal, wave and wind energy systems at the forefront of sustainable power generation. Permanent magnet synchronous generators with high efficiency, modularity, and low power consumption, such as the lightweight and modular C-GEN design, have been applied successfully in these applications. The demagnetisation condition of nonadjacent magnets in direct-drive permanent magnet generators is investigated, and different diagnostic approaches are evaluated. It is shown that nonadjacent demagnetisation can produce false negative diagnostic alarms when familiar condition monitoring methods such as the MCSA are applied. It presents solutions for faulty magnet detection of permanent magnet generators for tidal, wave, and wind energy harvesting, supported by numerical analysis and experimental testing. It is particularly novel that demagnetisation in two nonadjacent magnets is investigated here, something not previously considered.

1 | Introduction

The continuous improvement in renewable energy technologies has given much attention to tidal, wave and wind energy sources. In these areas direct-drive permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs) are the key technology, mainly because of their high efficiency, compact design, and reduced maintenance requirements. Among these, the lightweight and modular C-GEN generator design has been successfully applied to various renewable energy applications as shown in ref. [1]. The C-GEN topology, developed at the University of Edinburgh, is a lightweight direct-drive PM generator in which each stator module is a toothless C-shaped back-iron core and the rotor carries surface-mounted NdFeB magnets on a thin drum. As the drum rotates, radial flux alternately links the modular C-cores and induces an EMF given by $E = N\omega\Phi$. The open air-

cored stator eliminates tooth ripple and attraction forces, enabling a large air-gap and a high torque-to-mass ratio that suits tidal, wave and low-speed wind converters. Because adjacent modules share the same back-iron, local loss of magnet strength forces a circulating current through healthy modules, providing a sensitive signature for demagnetisation diagnostics.

The variable and harsh operating conditions of tide and wave energy systems create challenges in these systems. Studies such as [1, 2] demonstrate that low-speed, high-torque generators are needed, which do not require complex gear systems but are reliable in submerged or coastal environments. Combining advanced modelling and optimisation techniques such as the one described in ref. [3], has led to robust designs of wave converters and tidal turbines with high energy conversion efficiency.

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Also, wind turbine energy generators have been popular because of their scalability and high energy yields, especially in offshore applications. The fractional frequency transmission system applied in ref. [2] and the advanced control mechanisms developed in refs. [4, 5] have significantly enhanced the operational efficiency and stability of wind energy systems.

Moreover, new black start control strategies for PMSG-based wind turbines [6] have resilience during grid outages, ensuring continuous power generation. However, as these systems become more complex, ensuring their reliability through effective fault detection becomes increasingly critical. Incipient fault detection is particularly vital in electrical machines, as undetected issues can escalate, leading to catastrophic failures and costly downtimes. This is because incipient faults will get progressively worse and may cause catastrophic failures, if not detected [7]. In addition, one fault may cause another to appear, and the two faults may form together, accelerating the failure's evolution. One such example is the strong correlation between the appearance of an inter-turn fault and subsequent demagnetisation of the rotor [8, 9].

This demagnetisation fault occurs on PM machines. Two conditions can permanently demagnetise permanent magnets. The first is thermal stress [10] and the second is overload of the machine [11]. In the former case, the B-H characteristic of permanent magnets depends on the operating temperature. Above some critical threshold, the remanence of the magnets decreases, and the magnets lose some of the magnetisation abilities. For the former, overloading will draw high current and produce opposing magnetic fields strong enough to cause irreversible

demagnetisation of the permanent magnets. The demagnetisation fault may be variable in severity. Assuming a fixed load, the machine will work at higher current to produce the same power. That means greater copper losses and higher operation temperatures may induce more demagnetisation until a critical current level is reached.

For all the reasons above, the demagnetisation fault and its detection have received considerable attention and research efforts within the diagnostics community because of its importance. In the past, fault detection methods have included MCSA (Motor Current Signature Analysis) [12], flux monitoring and other methods [13]. For a better understanding of the strengths and limitations of these methods, a comprehensive comparison is presented in Table 1. Although widely employed, MCSA acknowledged its limitations in detecting mechanical defects related to bearing, eccentricity, or load showing that vibration analysis is more reliable for such defects. Based on the current signature frequency spectrum processing, this method can identify various faults [17].

Analysis of either the airgap or stray flux is an excellent diagnostic procedure since it gives insight into the radial or axial flux asymmetry inducing faults directly on the machine. With components such as radial leakage flux and axial leakage flux, airgap flux monitoring shows higher sensitivity than the vibration analysis or the MCSA, in detecting faults such as shorted field winding turns, rotor conductor issues, and airgap eccentricity [7].

In the majority of published papers, the authors treat nonuniform demagnetisation. The reason is that the uniform one cannot be

TABLE 1 | Comparison of diagnostic methods for demagnetisation detection in PM generators.

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Motor current signature analysis (MCSA) [14]	Nonintrusive and easily implementable using standard equipment.	Dependent on machine geometry (e.g., pole number and winding configuration), leading to harmonic cancellation in some cases.
	Facilitates online and remote monitoring.	Ineffective for uniform demagnetisation, as it does not produce harmonics in the current spectrum.
	Suitable for detecting multiple types of faults (e.g., eccentricity, inter-turn faults).	Susceptible to noise, especially in cases of low-severity faults or nonadjacent demagnetisation.
Magnetic flux monitoring [15]	Direct measurement of magnetic field asymmetries; not reliant on winding configuration or pole number.	Requires installation of additional sensors, increasing system complexity and cost.
	Provides multiple fault-related signatures in the spectrum, improving detection reliability.	Data acquisition and processing can be challenging under certain conditions.
	Insensitive to harmonic cancellation, making it more robust for fault detection.	
Torque monitoring [16]	Allows detection of torque oscillations caused by demagnetisation faults.	Limited practical applicability due to difficulty in directly measuring shaft torque in real world systems.
	Can be performed indirectly using voltage and current measurements, offering nonintrusiveness.	Inconsistent results for nonadjacent demagnetisation faults; may lead to false negatives.
	Can be used in conjunction with vibration analysis to enhance fault diagnosis.	High noise levels in torque spectra can obscure fault-related signatures.

detected by spectral analysis because it does not produce relevant harmonics in the monitored signals. A trailing edge demagnetisation effect has been shown, and methods have been proposed to detect such a fault in PM motors [18]. The relevant stator current harmonics for the fault in high numbers of poles of PM generators are, therefore, dependent on poles and stator-concentrated windings [19, 20]. Also, possible misdiagnosis cases have been experimentally proven [21]. New works deal with fault detection in transient machine operation [22]. Moreover, much work has been done on the discrimination between the eccentricity and demagnetisation faults [23–26]. It is worth mentioning that the air-gap flux has been used in ref. [27] to discriminate between rotor faults and eccentricity in wound rotor synchronous machines, which is equivalent to demagnetisation and eccentricity identification. Finally, the connection between stator electrical faults and the development of demagnetisation has been investigated [28, 29].

This paper also extends early findings [30]. The new FEA model comes remarkably close to the experimental testing. Table 2 lists the key electrical and geometrical parameters used in the revised model, whereas Table 3 compares revised FEA results with experimental data and shows a much smaller phase voltage, current, and torque discrepancies, as well as improved overall efficiency. Confirming the accuracy of updated simulations through real world testing enhances the reliability and applicability of proposed diagnostic approaches for electromechanical systems.

Regarding this work, Section 2 describes the development and validation of the finite element analysis (FEA) model for the radial flux C-GEN generator, including steady-state and transient analyses. Section 3 provides basic equations and analysis on how nonadjacent demagnetisation induces harmonic cancellation in the stator currents. In Section 4, the electromagnetic analysis of circulating currents, losses and efficiency

TABLE 2 | PM generator nominal characteristics.

Rated Power (kW)	21.5
Rated Speed (rpm)	100
Stator	Coreless
Frequency (Hz)	26.67
Pole pairs	16
Stator coils	24 × single concentrated
Stator coil turns	205
Magnet material	N42

TABLE 3 | FEA model versus. real generator comparison.

Variable	FEA	Experiment	Difference
Phase voltage (V)	300.74	306.70	1.96%
Phase current (A)	17.19	17.41	1.29%
Torque (Nm)	1565	1575	0.51%
Output power (kW)	15.5	15.4	0.65%
Input power (kW)	16.5	16.5	0.05%

impacts due to demagnetisation faults is described. Section 5 describes the Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) results, including diagnostic challenges and false negatives. Section 6 describes alternative diagnostic approaches such as magnetic flux and torque monitoring to overcome MCSA limitations and compares the results of simulation and experiment. Section 8 concludes with a summary of the key results, implications for renewable energy systems and future directions of research.

2 | Model Development

To achieve a reliable electromagnetic analysis, a finite element analysis (FEA) model of a radial flux C-GEN generator has been designed. The model captures the key geometry and materials of the generator, including its dual-rotor layout: each rotor carries 32 surface-mounted magnets set at an 11.25° electrical pole pitch, with a 1.2 mm radial air-gap between adjacent magnets on the same drum. Particularly, the simulation environment considers the magnetic permeability of the core materials, the geometric configuration of the rotor and stator, and the boundary conditions that mimic the real machine operation environment.

Figure 1 presents the finite-element (FEA) model of the C-GEN generator, illustrating (a) magnetic flux distribution, (b) the corresponding cross-sectional geometry, and (c) key topology dimensions. This figure shows some of the flux concentration paths and regions of magnetic saturation which are important to predict the performance of the generator under various load conditions. The nominal characteristics of the generator rated power, speed, and voltage are summarised in Table 2 as a benchmark for expected performance.

Besides steady-state analysis, transient electromagnetic behaviour was investigated to evaluate the generator dynamic response during startup and load changes. Those analyses involved simulating the time-varying currents and voltages inside the generator to verify that the model can predict the performance under nonstationary condition accurately.

The FEA model was confirmed by an experimental campaign on a real machine prototype. This experiment setup required precise instrumentation to measure magnetic flux density and electrical output in controlled condition. Table 3 compares the simulated and experimental results together with the calculated percentile differences. These comparisons show that the simulated machine describes the real one reasonably well, confirming the model reliability for further electromagnetic studies.

Additionally, sensitivity analyses were performed to identify the effects of key parameters on model output. The effects of these variations on the magnetic flux distribution were introduced and compared. Results reveal that although local flux concentrations differ significantly due to small variations in these parameters, the performance metrics of the generator are still acceptable.

In this expanded section, the robustness of simulation model is also highlighted and provides a basis for the further analysis of generator performance and the discussion of fault diagnosis and monitoring strategies later in the article.

FIGURE 1 | FEA model of the C-GEN generator where: (a) magnetic flux distribution and (b) cross-sectional model and (c) topology dimensions ($t_w = 20 \text{ mm}$, $h_{PM} = 16 \text{ mm}$ and $g = 5 \text{ mm}$).

3 | Harmonics Cancellation due to Nonadjacent Demagnetised Magnets

It has been shown [19] that the magnetic flux density due to demagnetisation of a single magnet is given by the following:

$$B(\theta, t) = a_k \sum_{n=2m+1}^{\infty} F_{PM} \cos(np\theta - n\omega_s t - \varphi_n) + \beta_k \sum_{n=2m+1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} F_{PM} A_k \left\{ \cos \left[(np - k)\theta - \left(n - \frac{k}{p} \right) \omega_s t - \varphi_n \right] + \cos \left[(np + k)\theta - \left(n + \frac{k}{p} \right) \omega_s t - \varphi_n \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

where a_k and β_k are constants depending on geometrical features of the electrical machine. Because of the change of the magnetic flux, voltage will be induced in the stator coils due to Faraday's Law of Induction as follows:

$$V_{\text{dmg}} = \sum_{n=2m+1}^{\infty} V_n \cos(np\theta - n\omega_s t - \varphi_n) + \sum_{n=2m+1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} V_{nk} \left\{ \cos \left[(np - k)\theta - \left(n - \frac{k}{p} \right) \omega_s t - \varphi_n \right] + \cos \left[(np + k)\theta - \left(n + \frac{k}{p} \right) \omega_s t - \varphi_n \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

Assuming two magnets at nonadjacent positions and apart by one rotor pole pitch, leads to the conclusion that while one demagnetised magnet affects a coil of one phase, the second one affects a different phase, while the induced voltages due to the fault are in opposite phases with each other. Considering that the stator winding is in star, the summation of the fault induced voltages will result in zero, thus no demagnetisation fault signatures are expected in the stator currents.

It is important to clarify that the possibilities of nonadjacent demagnetised magnet conditions that may lead to false negative diagnostic alarms via the stator current analysis are infinite, as different magnets and fault severities can lead to the same negative diagnostic outcome.

4 | Electromagnetic Analysis

FEA simulations are used to calculate the circulating currents and offer a deeper understanding of the phenomenon. This is accomplished by subtracting the current of healthy and faulty coils. The resulting signals cannot be measured in real life, however they offer an insight into the amplitude, harmonics and impact of any parasitic currents that flow in a circular way between the stator coils. The phase winding consists of 8 coils divided in two in-series subgroups, each consisting of 4 coils in parallel. When the demagnetisation fault appears, the coils receive different electromotive forces from the rotor at every instant. However, the coil voltage must be the same due to the parallel connection. This means that the parallel loops will carry circulating currents. The best way to demonstrate their impact is to calculate the current difference between the healthy and faulty state at every time. The circulating currents of the 4 parallel coil currents when the machine experiences a demagnetised magnet (25% fault severity) have a phase shift over time which depends on the rotor speed [30].

Magnetic asymmetry is expected to affect the generator's losses and efficiency [31]. This has also been investigated here, and interesting outcomes have been generated. Tables 4 and 5 present the analysis results. Firstly, the impact of the fault on the power efficiency is shown in the last column of both tables. The three-phase ohmic resistance increases with increasing load because the same electromotive force drives a smaller current, thereby reducing power transfer. Conversely, if resistance is low, the load is increased because higher current is drawn. Thus, demagnetisation faults affect the efficiency of the generator more adversely under low load conditions due to the greater relative impact of circulating currents and associated losses. This is attributed to the circulating currents. Because the generator has the same speed in both loading cases, the electromotive force is the same. Therefore, the induced circulating currents have similar losses in both cases, however the total losses are different due to the different stator currents required by the different loads. As a result, the less the load, the stronger the fault's impact on efficiency. This is supported by Figure 2, depicting a coil's current difference under three different loads. The circulating current proves to be the same in all cases.

5 | MCSA Results

The generator has been simulated to operate under various faulty conditions. Firstly, only one magnet has been demagnetised by two different severity levels (25% and 50%). Then, two nonadjacent magnets were demagnetised. The two magnets are apart by one bipolar pitch. The two faulty magnets have been set to have equal severities (both 25% and 50%) as well as different (one 25% and the other 50%). The reason is that it has been shown in past works [19] that demagnetised magnets at specific locations on the rotor may lead to false negative diagnostic alarms when the MCSA is applied.

The MCSA results are shown in Figure 3 for all the studied cases. Because of Equations (3-5) [19], the expected harmonics, indicative of demagnetisation, are located at $f_s - \frac{f_s}{2}$ and $2f_s$ for this machine topology.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_{dmg1} = \left(n \pm \frac{2\delta \cdot \epsilon}{p} \right) f_s, \text{ produced due to coils at } \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (3) \\ f_{3ph_null} = \frac{3\gamma_{ph} \cdot \lambda'}{p} f_s, \text{ cancelled due to 3 - phases} \quad (4) \\ f_{dmg2} = \left(n \pm \frac{3\kappa}{p} \right) f_s, \text{ produced due to 3x coils} \quad (5) \end{array} \right.$$

Table 6 gives the amplitudes for fault-related harmonics. For one demagnetised magnet (DM), both harmonic signatures increase with fault severity. The harmonic at twice the fundamental frequency never attains sufficient high amplitude and may be masked by noise in practice, however. In contrast, the left sideband shows an obvious and significant amplitude, which is useful for diagnosis. Conversely, the expected prominent left sideband is not exhibited when two magnets are equally demagnetised separated by one bipolar pitch the amplitude is similar to that of the healthy machine. Meanwhile, the right sideband increases with fault severity, but its amplitude becomes diagnostically significant only when the fault is severe.

Despite visually similar MCSA plots for the 25% and 50% demagnetisation cases (Figure 2 a,b, and e), Table 6 shows distinct amplitude rises at $f_s/2$ and $2f_s$. In particular, at $(f_s - f_s/2)$ for 25% demagnetisation, the amplitude is about -48.76 dB, and it is about -42.68 dB for 50% demagnetisation. At $2f_s$ this same trend is apparent. Though inherent measurement instrument errors may obscure such differences in real world applications, the observed amplitude changes are large enough to exceed the noise floor. Accordingly, the severity of demagnetisation can be distinguished in practice.

TABLE 4 | Losses and efficiency-rated load.

Machine condition	Joule losses/input	Magnetic losses/input	Efficiency (%)
Healthy	4.01%	2.31%	93.68
1 DM-25%	4.15%	2.37%	93.48
1 DM-50%	4.56%	2.55%	92.90
2 DM-25% and 50%	4.64%	2.60%	92.76
2 DM-25%	4.26%	2.42%	93.32
2 DM-50%	4.99%	2.77%	92.23

TABLE 5 | Losses and efficiency-75% of rated load.

Machine condition	Joule losses/input	Magnetic losses/input	Efficiency (%)
Healthy	3.25%	1.90%	94.85%
1 DM-25%	3.42%	1.98%	94.60%
1 DM-50%	3.93%	2.20%	93.87%
2 DM-25% and 50%	4.03%	2.27%	93.70%
2 DM-25%	3.56%	2.05%	94.40%
2 DM-50%	4.47%	2.48%	93.05%

FIGURE 2 | Current difference, between faulty and healthy condition, of a random stator coil for the generator suffering from one demagnetised magnet by 50%, where (a) 25% more resistive load, (b) rated load and (c) 25% less resistive load [30].

6 | Alternative Diagnostic Approaches

The MCSA cannot deliver reliable diagnostic outcomes under certain fault conditions, so other ways of improving fault detection reliability must be investigated. Two additional electromagnetic variables of the generator magnetic flux and torque are considered in this simulation study. These spectral results are obtained completely through simulation and thus provide a controlled environment to evaluate the performance and limitations of such diagnostic approaches as compared to MCSA-based results.

6.1 | Magnetic Flux Analysis

It is important to clarify that the MCSA is, in a way, a flux monitoring technique. The stator winding is the magnetic flux

FIGURE 3 | MCSA results for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: (a) 1 demagnetised magnet by 25%, (b) 1 demagnetised magnet by 50%, (c) 2 nonadjacent demagnetised magnets by 25%, (d) 2 nonadjacent demagnetised magnets by 50% and (e) one demagnetised magnet by 25% and a nonadjacent by 50%.

TABLE 6 | MCSA–fault signatures amplitudes.

Machine condition	$f_s - f_s/2$	$2f_s$
Healthy	−112.67 dB	−121.62 dB
1 DM–25%	−48.76 dB	−74.99 dB
1 DM–50%	−42.68 dB	−69.01 dB
2 DM–25%	−113.41 dB	−68.95 dB
2 DM–50%	−113.07 dB	−62.93 dB
2 DM–25% and 50%	−48.66 dB	−65.44 dB

sensor that senses asymmetries of the magnetic field in the form of induced voltages and therefore the harmonic index of the flowing current is affected by them. However, the inherent disadvantage of MCSA is its dependence on the machine's number of poles. In other words, the spatial distribution of the winding in accordance with the magnetic poles of the machine, is the main reason behind the harmonic cancellation in many diagnostic cases. This drawback does not exist in the flux monitoring methodologies because the sensor geometry is not related to the number of magnetic poles. As a result, harmonic cancellation phenomena are absent from this procedure. Specifically, in this study flux monitoring relies on sensors mounted on the stator coils sensing the air-gap flux.

The spectral results are shown in Figure 4. Firstly, the obvious advantage of the flux over the stator current is that due to the lack of harmonic cancellation, multiple signatures of the fault appear in the spectra. Specifically, when only one magnet is affected, harmonics of frequency $f_s \pm k \frac{f_s}{p}$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, appear in the faulty machine. Those harmonics' amplitudes are around −52 dB for fault severity 25% and increase by about 7 dB for 50% severity. Furthermore, when two nonadjacent magnets exist at a bipolar distance, we can see a cancellation phenomenon at frequencies $f_s \pm \frac{f_s}{2}$. Despite that, all the other signatures are present and can reveal the fault. Their amplitudes are not almost uniform as those when only one magnet is demagnetised though. The signatures follow an oscillating pattern, with progressive weakening of their amplitude close to the cancellation frequencies. Finally, when the two nonadjacent bars are faulty but by different severity levels, there is no cancellation phenomenon, however the amplitudes are also oscillating along the frequency.

6.2 | Torque Analysis

Electrical machine torque analysis for fault detection received little attention in the past years. Of course, there exist course papers in the field [32], but in real applications torque monitoring has not been adopted because it is practically impossible to measure the shaft torque directly. That said, the electromagnetic torque spectra may be estimated using 3-phase voltage and current monitoring. Therefore, this method is nonintrusive, online, and remote monitoring is possible.

FIGURE 4 | Flux monitoring results for faulty cases (red) versus healthy (black) where: (a) 1 demagnetised magnet by 25%, (b) 1 demagnetised magnet by 50%, (c) 2 nonadjacent demagnetised magnets by 25%, (d) 2 nonadjacent demagnetised magnets by 50% and (e) one demagnetised magnet by 25% and a nonadjacent by 50%.

Herein, the torque spectra of studied cases are analysed. The spectra for all cases are shown in Figure 5. This field interaction between the main rotor magnetic field and the new stator fields will produce torque oscillations at frequencies: $f_s + \frac{f_i}{2}$ and $f_s + 2f_s$. They are about 40 and 80 Hz, respectively here. The corresponding amplitudes are shown in Table 7. For early faults such as a single magnet demagnetisation, the amplitude increase of the first signature is greater than 40 dB. The second signature is larger but has low amplitude. The two adjacent demagnetised magnets affect the first signature amplitude but do not cancel it out completely. When the fault severity is increased by 50%, the amplitude is clearly higher than that of the healthy machine. So, the fault is detected, but its severity is not known.

Its outcomes depend on vibration analysis. For this particular case, the torque is a better signal than the stator current from a diagnostic point of view but not ideal.

7 | Experimental Results From a Direct-Drive Permanent Magnet Generator

7.1 | Experimental Lay-Out and Instrumentation

The experimental setup was designed to capture key performance metrics across a wide range of operating conditions. The C-GEN generator has been mechanically coupled to an inverter fed induction motor. The output electric power is then consumed in a 3-phase variable ohmic load bank. The tested generator is shown in Figure 6 below.

Measurements have been performed, for rotational speeds ranging from 10 to 100 rpm and power outputs between 1 and 30 kW. This range was chosen to ensure that the system's behaviour under both low and high loading conditions could be comprehensively analysed. Among the recorded data, the figures corresponding to 100 rpm and 10 kW provided the most representative results. These operating points were for capturing fault-related phenomena and maintaining clarity in the measured signals, offering a clear validation of the simulation results. The data at this specific operating condition exhibited the clearest fault signatures, making it ideal for validating the system's diagnostic methods. Our experimental tests simulate the demagnetisation defect by physically removing the steel plate containing one magnet from one of the two rotors. We thus create a localised area where the magnetic contribution is absent. Such removal decreases the overall magnetic flux in that area to about 50% of normal. It corresponds to having a 50% demagnetisation fault when measured in the middle of the air gap. Such an approach allows for a controlled and reproducible way of modelling demagnetisation to evaluate the diagnostic methods under realistic fault conditions. The magnetic flux was measured using rectangular shape search coils with turn number equal to 1000 turns. The search coil was placed on the end winding of the generator which entails sensing of the radial component of the leakage flux. The reduced remanent magnetic flux density of the demagnetised magnet in combination with the magnetic flux

FIGURE 5 | Torque monitoring results for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: (a) 1 demagnetised magnet by 25%, (b) 1 demagnetised magnet by 50%, (c) 2 nonadjacent demagnetised magnets by 25%, (d) 2 nonadjacent demagnetised magnets by 50% and (e) one demagnetised magnet by 25% and a nonadjacent by 50%.

TABLE 7 | Torque signatures' amplitudes (dB).

Machine condition	$f_s + \frac{f_s}{2}$	$f_s + 2f_s$
Healthy	-103.02	-123.49
1 DM-25%	-51.84	-77.94
1 DM-50%	-47.95	-67.96
2 DM-25%	-72.41	-72.72
2 DM-50%	-60.38	-62.53
2 DM-25% and 50%	-53.05	-66.53

FIGURE 6 | The tested radial flux C-GEN.

generated by the circulating currents would cause a signal in the search coil that would later be processed. To acquire the signals of the stator current, a data-acquisition-system employing current probes has been adopted. More specifically, a Pico Scope 4824 data acquisition system connected with a Pico TA167 oscilloscope probe is used to sample the stator current signal with a sampling frequency of 10 kHz. The voltage signal in the stator search coil is measured using a voltage probe. The characteristics of the voltage probe are TESTEC TT-LF 312 with 1:1 scaling, attenuation ratio x1, input impedance 47 pF, Bandwidth 15 MHz, rise time 24 nsec, and compensation range 10–60 pF. Both voltage and current probes measure and connect with the DAQ, which utilises a laptop computer as a user interface, allowing the display of the signal in time.

7.2 | Comparison Between Simulations and Experiments

7.2.1 | Stator Current Signature Analysis

The calculated spectra of the stator current, while the generator operates under 10 kW load at 100 rpm are shown in Figure 7. More specifically, in Figure 8a, the current spectra depict the healthy (black) generator versus the case of a generator with a single faulty magnet. Furthermore, in Figure 8b, the healthy generator spectrum is compared to that of the generator with two faulty magnets located at nonadjacent positions (2 pole-pitch). It is evident that when a single magnet is faulty and due to the specific topology of the generator, only the signature at $\frac{f_s}{2}$ increases in amplitude by a significant amount (~ 20 dB). This result fully agrees with the simulation results.

b)**FIGURE 8** | Experimental MCSA results for the generator at 100 rpm 10kw where for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: (a) 1 defected magnet (b) 2 nonadjacent defected magnets.

The fault signature's amplitude is shown in Table 8 for all the studied cases. Interestingly, the signature does not increase in the case of nonadjacent faulty magnets, as predicted earlier by

TABLE 8 | Current signatures' amplitudes at $\frac{f_s}{2}$ (dB).

Loading at 100 rpm (kW)	Healthy	1 DM	2 DM (nonadjacent)
2	-55.13	-33.76	-53.03
4	-53.33	-33.87	-53.33
5	-54.49	-33.77	-55.45
10	-54.17	-33.69	-56.26

the FEA simulations (Figure 3c,d). Additionally, one can see the existence of 4 sidebands around the fundamental, at frequencies: $f_s \pm \frac{k f_s}{p}$, where $k = 1, 2$. These harmonics are irrelevant for the detection of demagnetisation and they are caused by rotor imbalance and eccentricity, when the steel plates are removed to create the magnetic defects.

7.2.2 | Stray Flux Monitoring

The experimental results from the flux monitoring approach closely align with the simulation outcomes, confirming the presence of multiple harmonic signatures in the faulty machine. As expected, harmonics were detected at frequencies $f_s \pm k \frac{f_s}{p}$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, with similar amplitude patterns corresponding to varying fault severity levels (Figure 7). It is interesting that in the case of nonadjacent defects, the signature at $f_s - \frac{9f_s}{p}$ becomes equal to that of the healthy machine. This outcome was not observed in the simulations and it is related to the co-existence and weakening of two different components, namely the demagnetisation signature $f_s - \frac{9f_s}{p}$ and the eccentricity one $\frac{f_s}{2} - \frac{f_s}{p}$. Moreover, the signature at $\frac{f_s}{2}$ comes close to the healthy one when nonadjacent defects exist and verifies the simulation results (Figure 4c,d) where this signature was completely absent in the nonadjacent faulty cases matching the healthy generator. The amplitudes of the various fault signatures have been extracted and presented in Table 9 and in Figure 9 for better understanding. Similarly with the stator current, it is shown that the introduced eccentricity gave an extra amplitude rise to the $f_s - \frac{f_s}{p}$ and the $f_s - \frac{2f_s}{p}$ components, making the dominant in the spectra of the nonadjacent defected magnets case.

7.2.3 | Torque Monitoring

A torque transducer was coupled between the shafts of the induction motor and the generator, to monitor the mechanical torque. The experimental results for torque analysis show a close match with the simulation, especially regarding the oscillations at the main fault signature at $f_s + \frac{f_s}{2}$ (marked by an arrow in Figure 10). This signature has an amplitude of -66.78 dB in the healthy machine, and it increases by 17 dB in the case of a single defected magnet (Figure 10a). However, this signature has a weak increase of approximately 6 dB when two nonadjacent defected magnets exist on the rotor (Figure 10b). This is similar with the simulation results and leads to the conclusion that the torque signal has similar disadvantages with the stator's current when it comes to nonadjacent defected magnets.

TABLE 9 | Experimental flux signatures' amplitudes (dB).

Frequency	Healthy	1 DM	2 DM (nonadjacent)
$f_s - \frac{15 f_s}{16}$	-29.60	-26.37	-21.80
$f_s - \frac{14 f_s}{16}$	-26.41	-21.50	-19.14
$f_s - \frac{13 f_s}{16}$	-28.28	-13.66	-12.89
$f_s - \frac{12 f_s}{16}$	-22.57	-9.01	-10.73
$f_s - \frac{11 f_s}{16}$	-26.35	-8.16	-11.57
$f_s - \frac{10 f_s}{16}$	-31.36	-9.43	-15.41
$f_s - \frac{9 f_s}{16}$	-21.99	-5.12	-22.89
$f_s - \frac{8 f_s}{16}$	-27.82	-7.92	-15.92
$f_s - \frac{7 f_s}{16}$	-26.69	-8.32	-12.82
$f_s - \frac{6 f_s}{16}$	-28.10	-5.28	-5.55
$f_s - \frac{5 f_s}{16}$	-40.44	-6.62	-4.29
$f_s - \frac{4 f_s}{16}$	-26.28	-7.33	-2.71
$f_s - \frac{3 f_s}{16}$	-27.96	-5.74	-0.57
$f_s - \frac{2 f_s}{16}$	-25.43	-5.53	0
$f_s - \frac{1 f_s}{16}$	-26.60	-6.06	-1.24
f_s	0	0	-7.55

8 | Conclusions

This work presents an investigation of electromagnetic behaviour and the diagnostic potential of direct-drive permanent magnet generators under demagnetisation faults, focusing on a novel case nonadjacent demagnetised magnets not previously investigated. We show through simulation and experiment that traditional Motor Current Signature Analysis and torque monitoring can produce false negatives under certain fault conditions. For instance, when one magnet is demagnetised at both a 25% and 50% severity level, the diagnostic harmonic amplitude increases clearly. But when two nonadjacent magnets are demagnetised equally, the critical left sideband cancels out giving an amplitude almost identical to that of a healthy machine. Alternatively, one magnet is demagnetised by 25%, and the other by 50%, and the amplitude increase is apparent but less definite than in the single-fault case.

Additionally, although torque monitoring shows some sensitivity to demagnetisation faults, its diagnostic reliability is also compromised by nonadjacent faults, since it fails to differentiate between healthy and faulty conditions. By contrast, magnetic flux monitoring shows no harmonic cancellation such as MCSA and consistently reports several fault signatures that are related to the demagnetisation severity.

These findings suggest that they cannot be relied upon exclusively for stator current or torque-based diagnostics when nonadjacent demagnetisation faults exist. An enhanced finite element model validated against experimental data shows that magnetic flux monitoring is a robust and reliable solution for fault detection in direct-drive permanent magnet generators

FIGURE 9 | Bar chart for experimental flux monitoring results for the generator at 100 rpm 10kw where for faulty cases (1 demagnetised magnet (red) and 2 nonadjacent defected magnets (yellow)) versus the healthy (blue).

a)

b)

FIGURE 10 | Experimental torque monitoring results for the generator at 100 rpm 10kw where for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: (a) 1 demagnetised magnet (b) 2 nonadjacent defected magnets.

especially in the harsh operating conditions of tidal, wave, and offshore wind energy systems.

Future works will entail improved fault severity quantification and integrated diagnostic strategies combining the strengths of different techniques to overcome the limitations of conventional methods.

Author Contributions

Alexandros Sergakis: conceptualization, validation, writing – original draft preparation, writing – review and editing. **Georgios A. Skarmoutsos:** validation, methodology. **Markus Mueller:** conceptualization, writing – review and editing, funding acquisition. **Konstantinos N. Gyftakis:** methodology, validation, writing – review and editing, funding acquisition.

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Ethics Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Consent

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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